

Dissociation Constants of Propionic Acid in Ethanol-Water Media at different Temperatures and related Thermodynamic Quantities

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Manuscript received 3 April 1989, accepted 9 August 1989

Dissociation constants of propionic acid in ethanol-water media containing 10, 20, 30, 45, 60 and 75 mass% of ethanol at 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35° have been determined using the cell,

The related thermodynamic quantities for the dissociation process at 25° have been calculated. The pK_a values of propionic acid at all the five temperatures increase as the proportion of organic component in the medium increases. In media with any particular composition, pK_a over the temperature range passes through a minimum.

In much of the literature on weak electrolytes, the entire focus is on the determination of the dissociation constants. For the estimation of the standard potentials of propionate reversible electrode in ethanol-water media, a knowledge of the dissociation constant (K_a) of propionic acid is necessary. Dissociation constants of acetic acid and propionic acid in water and dioxane-water media were reported by Harned and coworkers¹⁻⁵. Harned and Embree⁶ determined the value of K_a in 10 and 20 wt% of methanol at different temperatures. Bates and coworkers⁷ determined the values of pK_a over a temperature range 10-40° in 50 wt% methanol. Patterson and Felsing⁸ determined the values of K_a of propionic acid only in 10 and 20 wt% of methanol and ethanol-water mixtures at different temperatures. In this communication we report the dissociation constants of propionic acid in 10, 20, 30, 45, 60 and 75 mass% of ethanol at 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35°.

Experimental

Propionic acid (L.R., B.D.H.) was fractionally distilled twice, and the middle portion that constituted one-third of the amount of the distillate was retained each time. Finally the distillate (500 cm³) was mixed with potassium permanganate (A.R.; 10 g) and distilled and the middle fraction of the distillate was collected. Ethanol (99.5%) was prepared by dehydration of rectified spirit (95%) by freshly burnt quick lime⁹. Stock of hydrochloric acid was prepared by distilling hydrochloric acid (A.R.) with stannous chloride. The distillate was

then redistilled with double-distilled water to get a constant boiling mixture of hydrochloric acid and was standardised.

Double-distilled water was used throughout. Solvent mixtures of various percentage were freshly prepared before each experiment. The silver-silver chloride electrodes used were of thermal electrolytic type and prepared by the method recommended by Bates⁹. Cells of the type similar to that used by Harned and Ehlers¹⁰,

were used in the present measurements. Buffered solutions were used in the cell since the errors¹¹⁻¹⁴ that vitiate the dissociation constants of polybasic acids from the use of buffered solutions because of ion association of polyvalent anions, does not arise in the case of propionic acid. The measurements were taken at five temperatures, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35° with a Leeds-Northrup K_a potentiometer and galvanometer. The e.m.f. values reported are the average of four readings obtained from the combination of two silver-silver chloride and two hydrogen electrodes. All the e.m.f. readings were corrected to 1 atm pressure of hydrogen.

The vapour pressure of the mixed solvent was determined by graphical interpolation⁵ using the data from Landolt-Bornstein tables and densities of the mixed solvents at different temperatures were taken from literature¹⁶. The e.m.f. values at 25° at the start and at the completion of measurements

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(back to 25° again) agreed within 0.05 mV (average of four readings).

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of the cell is related to the concentration of hydrogen ion, m_H and that of chloride ion, m_{Cl^-} , by equation (1),

$$E = E^0 - \frac{RT}{F} \ln m_H \cdot m_{Cl^-} \cdot \gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{Cl^-} \quad (1)$$

where E^0 is the standard potential of Ag-AgCl electrode and γ_H and γ_{Cl^-} are the activity coefficients of hydrogen and chloride ions respectively. The standard potential of Ag-AgCl electrode was determined¹⁷ in our laboratory. In equation (1), $m_H \gamma_H$ may be eliminated by introducing the expression for the dissociation constant of propionic acid ($HOPr \rightleftharpoons H^+ + OPr^-$) which is expressed in equation (2),

$$K_a = \frac{m_H + m_{OPr^-} \cdot \gamma_H \gamma_{OPr^-}}{m_{HOPr} \cdot \gamma_{HOPr}} \quad (2)$$

The equation then reduces to equation (3),

$$\frac{(E - E^0)F}{2.3026 RT} + \log m_{Cl^-} m_{HOPr} = -\log K_a - \log \frac{\gamma_{Cl^-} \gamma_{HOPr}}{\gamma_{OPr^-}} \quad (3)$$

where $m_{Cl^-} = m_s =$ molality of NaCl, $m_{HOPr} = (m_1 - m_H)$ and $m_{OPr^-} = (m_2 + m_H)$. m_1 and m_2 represent the molalities of propionic and sodium propionate respectively. Since dissociation of HOPr is negligible and $\gamma_{Cl^-} = \gamma_{OPr^-}$

$$\frac{(E - E^0)F}{2.3026 RT} + \log \frac{m_1 m_2}{m_s} = -\log K_a - \log \gamma_{HOPr} \quad (4)$$

Long and McDevit¹⁸ discussed that for buffer solutions, the effect of salt on the activity coefficient of acetic acid or any molecular species can be represented by

$$\log \gamma_{HOPr} = SI \quad (5)$$

where I is the ionic strength of the solution and S the salting coefficient. Thus we have,

$$\frac{(E - E^0)F}{2.3026 RT} + \log \frac{m_1 m_2}{m_s} = -\log K_a - SI \quad (6)$$

Left-hand-side of the equation (6) is denoted by $-\log K'_a$. From the equation, it is apparent that the plot of $-\log K'_a$ against the I is linear, and the intercept at zero ionic strength gives $-\log K_a$ and hence K_a the thermodynamic dissociation constant.

Table 1 presents the e.m.f. values corrected to 1 atm pressure against molalities. Table 2 contains the values of $-\log K'_a$ and the corresponding I . The extrapolated pK_a values are in good agreement with that calculated by least-square method. The maximum uncertainty in the measurement is ± 0.002 per unit, and the individual deviation is less than this.

TABLE 1—E.M.F. VALUES OF THE CELL CORRECTED TO 1 ATM PRESSURE OF H_2 AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN ETHANOL-WATER MEDIA

Strength m_1 mol kg ⁻¹	E (V)				
	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
10 mass% ethanol					
0.097 69	0.567 83	0.570 46	0.574 50	0.577 49	0.581 61
0.084 21	0.571 31	0.573 81	0.577 77	0.581 29	0.585 30
0.070 67	0.575 41	0.578 01	0.582 09	0.585 34	0.589 36
0.057 13	0.580 21	0.583 38	0.587 22	0.590 98	0.594 91
0.048 98	0.586 21	0.589 98	0.593 96	0.597 21	0.601 35
0.036 91	0.590 49	0.594 38	0.599 29	0.601 60	0.605 80
0.030 10	0.595 53	0.599 38	0.603 67	0.606 94	0.611 25
0.024 08	0.601 09	0.605 00	0.609 34	0.612 69	0.616 95
0.017 36	0.609 25	0.613 11	0.617 73	0.621 08	0.625 60
0.009 83	0.623 29	0.627 39	0.632 33	0.635 67	0.640 57
0.003 08	0.651 99	0.656 63	0.662 13	0.665 69	0.671 10
20 mass% ethanol					
0.098 85	0.564 53	0.568 74	0.571 99	0.575 40	0.578 99
0.085 37	0.567 83	0.571 97	0.575 15	0.578 56	0.582 23
0.071 58	0.571 72	0.576 03	0.579 33	0.582 75	0.586 45
0.580 02	0.576 72	0.581 26	0.584 53	0.587 94	0.591 78
0.044 36	0.582 95	0.587 53	0.590 98	0.594 44	0.598 30
0.037 61	0.586 92	0.591 50	0.594 94	0.598 38	0.602 31
0.032 93	0.589 98	0.594 62	0.598 04	0.601 39	0.605 71
0.026 24	0.595 04	0.599 97	0.603 74	0.607 31	0.611 44
0.024 22	0.597 18	0.602 06	0.605 98	0.609 55	0.613 72
0.017 48	0.605 06	0.610 16	0.613 90	0.617 64	0.622 05
0.010 67	0.617 14	0.622 61	0.626 47	0.630 47	0.634 84
30 mass% ethanol					
0.099 79	0.574 77	0.579 34	0.585 21	0.588 07	0.586 42
0.862 9	0.577 83	0.582 48	0.588 33	0.588 31	0.589 70
0.072 65	0.581 36	0.586 03	0.591 95	0.591 91	0.593 33
0.059 15	0.586 19	0.590 90	0.596 85	0.596 85	0.598 30
0.052 70	0.588 67	0.593 49	0.599 46	0.599 54	0.601 10
0.055 96	0.591 86	0.596 74	0.602 71	0.602 93	0.604 48
0.032 41	0.600 26	0.605 27	0.611 34	0.611 67	0.613 42
0.025 67	0.605 74	0.610 83	0.617 02	0.617 42	0.619 19
0.011 64	0.624 80	0.630 28	0.636 59	0.637 33	0.639 38
0.008 94	0.631 26	0.636 73	0.643 29	0.644 17	0.646 34
0.004 82	0.646 43	0.652 27	0.659 12	0.660 00	0.662 72
45 mass% ethanol					
0.100 59	0.585 74	0.590 55	0.592 16	0.593 68	0.596 44
0.085 39	0.589 00	0.593 82	0.595 41	0.596 97	0.599 70
0.077 80	0.591 22	0.596 07	0.597 74	0.599 43	0.602 06
0.070 20	0.593 23	0.598 10	0.599 67	0.601 55	0.604 16
0.054 93	0.598 70	0.603 61	0.605 36	0.607 26	0.610 20
0.040 73	0.605 62	0.610 87	0.612 43	0.614 25	0.617 46
0.025 54	0.616 80	0.621 86	0.623 95	0.626 08	0.628 73
0.010 91	0.637 19	0.642 73	0.644 97	0.647 56	0.650 95
0.006 15	0.651 37	0.657 16	0.659 60	0.662 11	0.665 89
0.003 13	0.667 63	0.673 51	0.676 28	0.679 16	0.683 05
60 mass% ethanol					
0.105 94	0.593 78	0.596 46	0.598 02	0.602 56	0.603 60
0.089 70	0.596 94	0.599 59	0.601 19	0.605 33	0.606 82
0.073 46	0.601 06	0.603 82	0.605 46	0.610 15	0.611 18
0.065 35	0.603 95	0.606 81	0.608 51	0.613 28	0.614 31
0.049 15	0.610 17	0.613 15	0.614 95	0.619 81	0.620 90
0.041 07	0.614 12	0.617 11	0.618 96	0.623 85	0.624 97
0.033 39	0.619 23	0.622 26	0.624 20	0.629 12	0.630 35
0.025 24	0.625 33	0.628 35	0.630 32	0.635 33	0.637 19
0.017 16	0.634 75	0.638 10	0.640 25	0.645 51	0.646 92
0.014 69	0.638 62	0.642 13	0.644 10	0.649 50	0.651 20
0.008 26	0.652 90	0.656 34	0.658 90	0.664 51	0.665 96

(Table 1 contd.)

(Table 2 contd.)

75 mass% ethanol					
0.098 72	0.605 05	0.609 51	0.610 99	0.614 80	0.617 90
0.090 88	0.606 56	0.610 97	0.612 43	0.615 27	0.618 57
0.081 84	0.609 57	0.613 02	0.614 48	0.617 79	0.620 68
0.073 64	0.611 12	0.615 66	0.617 08	0.620 40	0.623 34
0.065 04	0.613 67	0.618 16	0.619 61	0.623 00	0.625 98
0.056 68	0.616 89	0.621 43	0.622 87	0.626 23	0.629 21
0.048 22	0.620 24	0.624 82	0.626 20	0.629 63	0.632 59
0.039 85	0.624 54	0.629 19	0.630 65	0.634 12	0.637 14
0.030 76	0.630 85	0.635 60	0.636 89	0.640 44	0.643 64
0.022 33	0.638 35	0.643 15	0.644 84	0.648 52	0.651 62

60 mass% ethanol					
0.105 94	6.206 40	6.201 87	6.201 41	6.203 14	6.215 93
0.089 70	6.189 86	6.183 99	6.182 76	6.185 19	6.195 84
0.073 46	6.174 71	6.169 98	6.168 29	6.170 35	6.180 38
0.065 35	6.174 37	6.169 84	6.168 89	6.171 41	6.180 76
0.049 15	6.169 50	6.165 19	6.164 11	6.166 94	6.164 77
0.041 07	6.150 54	6.145 21	6.143 76	6.145 47	6.153 93
0.033 39	6.149 79	6.143 82	6.142 59	6.143 24	6.151 46
0.025 24	6.143 80	6.137 32	6.134 45	6.134 03	6.141 66
0.017 16	6.132 81	6.126 98	6.124 68	6.126 50	6.133 29
0.014 69	6.132 56	6.128 83	6.122 27	6.125 45	6.133 89
0.008 26	6.132 52	6.123 40	6.122 56	6.125 19	6.127 35
Std. dev.	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $-\log K'_a$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

I ($m_1 + m_2$) mol kg ⁻¹	$-\log K'_a$				
	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
10 mass% ethanol					
0.078 15	5.089 81	5.070 79	5.072 61	5.082 46	5.092 26
0.067 37	5.086 17	5.054 00	5.063 50	5.091 23	5.098 03
0.056 53	5.081 63	5.059 94	5.060 32	5.072 37	5.078 33
0.045 70	5.073 31	5.059 88	5.054 71	5.072 80	5.076 68
0.035 19	5.064 71	5.058 95	5.054 98	5.063 74	5.068 47
0.029 53	5.063 33	5.059 29	5.052 07	5.060 48	5.065 07
0.024 08	5.063 10	5.056 87	5.054 57	5.060 85	5.065 73
0.019 26	5.063 37	5.056 40	5.053 41	5.059 46	5.062 00
0.013 88	5.063 86	5.053 73	5.053 03	5.056 79	5.061 18
0.007 86	5.062 46	5.052 28	5.052 93	5.053 88	5.059 16
0.001 93	5.062 71	5.051 24	5.052 90	5.049 27	5.054 59
Std. dev.	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00

20 mass% ethanol					
0.079 09	5.176 29	5.165 43	5.165 26	5.172 20	5.174 41
0.068 29	5.170 33	5.157 36	5.155 08	5.161 13	5.163 69
0.057 26	5.161 82	5.150 72	5.149 26	5.154 31	5.156 28
0.046 42	5.158 07	5.149 29	5.145 91	5.149 44	5.152 23
0.035 49	5.150 56	5.140 64	5.138 36	5.140 76	5.142 21
0.030 09	5.148 23	5.137 16	5.133 50	5.134 60	5.136 23
0.026 34	5.144 13	5.133 98	5.129 31	5.130 30	5.134 06
0.020 99	5.134 01	5.126 42	5.126 89	5.126 65	5.129 03
0.019 38	5.136 68	5.127 56	5.128 26	5.129 35	5.131 72
0.013 98	5.132 69	5.125 16	5.121 31	5.123 05	5.126 24
0.008 53	5.129 57	5.124 70	5.119 28	5.120 73	5.120 91
Std. dev.	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00

30 mass% ethanol					
0.079 83	5.505 61	5.497 37	5.497 80	5.496 84	5.499 60
0.066 06	5.495 90	5.488 24	5.487 42	5.487 53	5.490 02
0.058 12	5.483 04	5.475 37	5.473 86	5.472 74	5.474 74
0.047 32	5.478 19	5.469 03	5.467 34	5.465 60	5.466 66
0.042 16	5.471 43	5.463 82	5.461 32	5.460 09	5.462 31
0.036 77	5.467 71	5.459 81	5.456 94	5.457 02	5.458 12
0.025 93	5.462 93	5.454 85	5.451 16	5.450 66	5.452 75
0.020 54	5.457 66	5.449 14	5.445 97	5.445 11	5.445 87
0.009 31	5.447 58	5.440 17	5.433 37	5.432 68	5.432 69
0.007 15	5.445 87	5.436 35	5.431 87	5.431 64	5.431 78
0.003 86	5.443 26	5.435 61	5.431 51	5.426 86	5.431 77
Std. dev.	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00

45 mass% ethanol					
0.080 47	5.840 04	5.836 03	5.836 31	5.835 10	5.841 83
0.068 31	5.826 06	5.821 18	5.820 04	5.818 75	5.824 01
0.062 24	5.824 31	5.819 34	5.819 01	5.819 15	5.822 28
0.056 16	5.814 83	5.809 71	5.807 03	5.809 79	5.811 92
0.043 94	5.804 09	5.797 83	5.796 57	5.798 11	5.804 14
0.032 59	5.795 18	5.792 93	5.786 31	5.784 56	5.793 00
0.020 44	5.788 09	5.779 22	5.778 89	5.778 56	5.775 63
0.003 73	5.775 44	5.768 56	5.764 63	5.766 21	5.768 82
0.004 92	5.774 46	5.767 67	5.762 77	5.759 23	5.764 23
0.002 55	5.772 84	5.762 86	5.758 68	5.756 67	5.758 79
Std. dev.	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00	0.002 00

75 mass% ethanol					
0.098 72	6.845 29	6.843 76	6.854 80	6.864 86	6.880 06
0.090 88	6.833 39	6.830 56	6.840 92	6.850 25	6.864 99
0.081 84	6.825 49	6.822 78	6.832 44	6.841 56	6.855 65
0.073 64	6.824 20	6.822 66	6.830 48	6.839 05	6.853 31
0.065 04	6.814 93	6.811 39	6.819 39	6.828 40	6.842 50
0.056 68	6.811 54	6.807 86	6.814 70	6.822 25	6.835 62
0.048 22	6.799 89	6.795 89	6.800 82	6.808 52	6.800 73
0.039 85	6.792 30	6.788 19	6.793 19	6.800 44	6.812 24
0.030 76	6.790 25	6.785 99	6.786 31	6.793 13	6.806 15
0.022 33	6.782 23	6.776 72	6.781 54	6.788 24	6.797 53
Std. dev.	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00	0.003 00

For any composition of medium, the pK_a values over the temperature range pass through a minimum¹⁰. The pK_a values at all the five temperatures (Table 3) increase as the proportion of the organic component in the medium increases. Similar observations have been reported by us and others for the variation of pK_a of acids of the type HA ($HA \rightleftharpoons H^+ + A^-$) with change in the dielectric constant of the aquo-organic media²⁰⁻²².

TABLE 3— pK_a VALUES FOR DISSOCIATION OF HOPF IN EtOH-H₂O MEDIA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

EtOH mass%	pK_a				
	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
10	5.056	5.051	5.049	5.050	5.053
	±0.002	±0.002	±0.001	±0.001	±0.001
20	5.124	5.117	5.114	5.113	5.115
	±0.001	±0.001	±0.001	±0.001	±0.001
30	5.440	5.432	5.427	5.425	5.426
	±0.001	±0.031	±0.001	±0.001	±0.001
45	5.769	5.761	5.757	5.756	5.758
	±0.001	±0.001	±0.001	±0.001	±0.001
60	6.122	6.116	6.113	6.115	6.120
	±0.002	±0.002	±0.002	±0.002	±0.002
75	6.764	6.758	6.758	6.763	6.774
	±0.002	±0.002	±0.002	±0.002	±0.002

The values of pK_a have been fitted to the equation¹⁰,

$$pK_a = \frac{A^*}{T} - D^* + C^* T \quad (7)$$

where T is temperature (K). Using the method of least-squares the values of A^* , C^* and D^* has been determined by solving the equations,

$$\sum \frac{\log K_a}{T} + A^* \sum \frac{1}{T^2} + SC^* - D^* \sum \frac{1}{T} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\sum T \log K_a + SA^* + C^* \sum T^2 - D^* \sum T = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\sum \log K_a + A^* \sum \frac{1}{T} + C^* \sum T - 5D^* = 0 \quad (10)$$

TABLE 4—VALUES OF CONSTANTS OF EQUATION (7) AND RELATED THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES FOR DISSOCIATION OF PROPIONIC ACID IN EtOH-H₂O MEDIA AT 25°

EtOH mass %	A*	C*	D*	C _p ^o J mol ⁻¹	ΔS ^o J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔH ^o J mol ⁻¹	ΔG ^o kJ mol ⁻¹
10	1 438.36	0.016 055	4.562 1	-188.3	-96.0	212.2	28.831
20	1 514.57	0 016 613	4.919 4	-189.7	-95.6	721.0	29.200
30	1 588.25	0.017 183	5.023 1	-196.2	-100.0	1 162.3	30.989
45	1 741.58	0 019 069	5.769 9	-217.7	-107 2	887.1	32.872
60	2 042.96	0.022 908	7.567 2	-261.5	-116 6	132.8	34.908
75	2 952.05	0 038 738	13.202 5	-385 2	-132.4	-905.0	38.588

With $-\log K_a$ expressed in the form of equation (7) we have the thermodynamic quantities, Gibbs free energy change (ΔG^o), the enthalpy change (ΔH^o), entropy change (ΔS^o) and heat capacity change (ΔC_p^o) for the dissociation process by standard procedure in the forms,

$$\Delta G^o = 2.3026 RT \log K_a$$

$$\Delta H^o = 2.3026 RA^* - 2.3026 RC^* T^2$$

$$\Delta C_p^o = -2 \times 2.3026 RC^* T$$

$$\text{and } \Delta S^o = 2.3026 RD^* + \Delta C_p^o$$

The thermodynamic values for the ionisation process at 25° in 10, 20, 30, 45, 60 and 75 mass% of ethanol-water system are given in Table 4.

In mixed solvent systems solvation causes very characteristic variations in ΔG^o , ΔH^o and ΔS^o . According to an earlier suggestion by Feakins and Watson²³ and a detailed analysis by Ben Naim²⁴, changes in solvent-solvent interactions in bulk solvent brought about by the ions will have a significantly larger influence in the enthalpy and entropy than on free energy values. Ionisation of neutral molecules into charged species, according to Frank and Evans²⁵, accompany a decrease in entropy due to the immobilisation of a large number of solvent molecules around the charged species. In the present study, as expected, we find a decrease in entropy all through. The entropy change is practically constant upto 20%. The small change around 30–45% ethanol may be the result of the difference in electrostatic effects on the process²⁶. Similar change was observed in the dissociation process of acetic acid in methanol-water media²⁰. This possibly indicates that up to 30% ethanol, the solvation of ions is by water molecules, and beyond 30% ethanol, ethanol molecules start competing with water molecules in the primary solvation sphere. The enthalpy change for the dissociation process also passes through a maximum around 30% ethanol, substantiating our assumption. ΔC_p^o for the dissociation process decreases with increase in the percentage of ethanol. Similar decreases have been observed in case of dissociation of formic, acetic and propionic acids in dioxane-water media²⁶.

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